

Attitude of Pre-Service Teachers Toward Utilization of Online Learning in Public Universities in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated attitude of pre-service teachers toward utilization of online learning in public universities in Ondo State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research designed was employed in the study. The study was guided by two research questions and one hypothesis. The population of the study comprised of all pre-service teachers in public universities in Ondo State. The sample for this comprised of 300 pre-service teachers randomly selected from the two public universities running education courses in the state. 150 pre-service teachers (undergraduates) were randomly selected in each of the 2 sampled schools, making a total of 300 participants. The instrument used in the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled “Pre-service Teachers’ Attitude and Utilization of Online Learning Questionnaire (PTAUOLQ)”. The instrument was validated by two lecturers in the field of test and measurement, while the reliability coefficient of instrument was determined using Cronbatch Alpha formula which the value of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to test the research questions raised in the study, while t-test was used to test the research hypothesis. The findings of the study revealed that pre-service teachers’ attitude towards online learning in the public universities in Ondo State is positive, with weighted average score is 2.92. It was also revealed that pre-service teachers’ level of utilization of online learning is high with weighted score of 2.52. It was further revealed that gender has no significant effect on pre-service teachers’ utilization of online learning in public universities. The study recommends that pre-service teachers should be exposed to periodic online training for learning to acquire necessary skills and develop positive attitude towards online learning. Also, both male and female pre-service teachers should be encouraged to use online learning in their academic programmes.

Keywords: Attitude, Online Learning, Utilization, Pre-service Teacher, Ondo State.

Introduction

The expansion of digital technologies, multimedia and other online tools have dramatically transformed education. In the last decade, the expansion of online learning has reached the educational field, which has led research to focus on exploring the potential of emerging technologies in virtual environments (Albrahim 2020). The advancement of digital technologies has allowed online learning to become an increasingly accessible and efficient educational modality. This technological transformation has facilitated the creation of flexible and personalised learning environments, improving accessibility and educational inclusion (Ali, 2020).

Online learning which is often refers to as electronic learning (e- learning) is defined as ‘learning experiences in synchronous or asynchronous environments using different devices (mobile phones, laptops and so and so forth). with internet access (Singh and Thurman, 2019). Folorunso, Ogunseye & Sharma (2006) describe online learning as spectrum of programme based on the internet that can be accessed in or out of school walls. There are two modes in online learning, which are synchronous and asynchronous depending on the application of applying optional timing of interaction. The synchronous online learning provides the direct interaction between the lecturers and students during class through tools such as videoconference or chat rooms. While asynchronous online learning provides the opportunity for the lecturers and students to interact before or after the online class through thread discussion and emails.

The prevalent convenience of the World Wide Web (WWW) and the comfort of using the apparatuses to browse the resources on the Web have made the online learning machinery immensely popular and the means of choice for distance education and professional exercise (Tariq & Rachna, 2018). Muirhead (2007) noted that online learning has continued to grow in higher education, with many universities placing greater emphasis on expanding access to online education.

Online learning is of great benefits for both teachers and learners. Through online learning methods and environments, students have a freedom in learning and get connected with their teachers anywhere they want (Singh & Thurman, 2019). Baytiyeh (2018) also claims that online learning make the teaching and learning of school subjects to be student-centred and also offers a great deal or flexibility in term of time and location. It enables modification of learning procedures and processes based on the needs of the students. The anywhere-any time features of online

education has great benefits in time of crisis-like situation such as man-made disasters, natural disasters or pandemic such as covid-19.

However, attitude of teachers is one of the factors that affect the successful implementation of online learning in education. Aderele and Abidoeye (2022) describe attitude as a learned disposition to respond in a consistently favourable or unfavorable manner with respect to a given subject, object or event. No matter how advanced or capable the technology is, its effective implementation depends upon users having a positive attitude toward it. Abidoeye and Aderele (2019), had identified various factors affecting teachers' attitudes towards the use of technologies in teaching and learning process. Such factors include; teachers' internal belief about the technology, organizational structure, technical factors such as complexity of a technology, environmental factors (or facilitating conditions) such as Information and Communications Technology (ICT) infrastructure, ICT features and support, years of teaching experience, academic qualification, gender and many more. Abidoeye and Fakuade (2025) claimed that pre-service teachers positive attitude towards an object will encourage the use of such object and reverse is the case when negative attitude is developed towards an object, event or situation.

Gender has been an important factor affecting the use of technology in teaching and learning process. Aderele and Abidoeye (2022), described gender as the socially constructed characteristics of women and men – such as norms, roles and relationships of and between groups of men (male) and women (female). Ogundare, Animasahun and Abidoeye (2022), also refers to gender as the socially and culturally constructed characteristics and roles which are ascribed to males and females in any society. He further explained that the male attributes as bold, aggressive, tactful, and efficient in the use of words while the females are fearful, shy, gentle, dull, submissive and effusive. Abidoeye & Fakuade (2025) also posit that there was a significant effect of gender on students' use of web-based learning such as online learning in favour of the male students than their female counterparts. Therefore, gender neutrality, friendliness or otherwise worth investigating especially at the public university level in Nigeria.

The level of pre service teachers' attitude and utilization of online learning tools are not ascertained in most of the public universities in Nigeria particularly in Ondo State because of the various challenges hindering effective use of online learning. It was also observed that there were few existing researches on pre-service teachers' use and attitude towards online learning in Ondo

State. Therefore, this study investigates attitude of pre-service teachers towards utilization of online learning in public Universities in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of the study

1. Determine the pre-service teachers' attitude towards online learning in public universities in Ondo State
2. Determine the pre-service teachers' level of utilization of online learning in public universities in Ondo State.
3. Determine the influence of gender differences on pre-service teachers' utilization of online learning in public universities in Ondo State.

Research Questions

Three research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the attitude of pre-service teachers toward online learning in public universities in Ondo State?
2. What is the level of pre-service teachers utilization of online learning in public universities in Ondo State?

Research Hypothesis

H01: There is no significant gender difference in the attitude of pre-service teachers toward utilization of online learning in public universities in Ondo State, Nigeria..

Research Methodology

The study employs a descriptive survey research design. The sample consisted of 300 pre-service teachers drawn from the two public universities running education courses (Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo and Adekunle Ajasin University Akungba Akoko, Ondo State). 150 undergraduate pre-service teachers were randomly selected from each of the two schools. The instrument used in the study was a 20-items questionnaire titled "Pre-service Teachers Attitude and Utilization of Online Learning Questionnaire (PTAUOLQ)". The instrument was divided into three sections, section A-C. Section A contains personal information about the respondents, section B elicits information about the attitude of Pre-service teachers towards online learning, while section C sought information about pre-service teachers' level of

utilization of online learning. It was a 4-points Likert Scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. The score of 4,3,2 and 1 were allotted and used respectively. The instrument was validated by two lecturers from the Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo. Cronbach alpha was used to establish the reliability of the instrument whose reliability coefficient yielded a value of 0.82 which was considered to be high enough for the instrument to be used in the study. Data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The three research questions raised in the study were answered with the use of mean and standard deviation. While the research hypothesis was tested with the use of t-test statistical tool.

Results

Research Question1: What is the attitude of pre-service teachers toward online learning in public universities in Ondo State?

Table 1: *Pre-Service Teachers' Attitude towards online learning in Public Universities in Ondo State.*

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.D
1	I dislike online learning because it is time consuming	26	73	123	78	2.15	.91
2	Online learning makes getting information easier	75	188	0	37	3.00	.86
3	Information through online are accurate	151	79	0	70	3.03	1.20
4.	I did not use online learning because it is expensive	138	107	18	37	3.15	.98
5.	I prefer conventional teaching mode to online learning because it is not accessible easily.	18	95	150	37	2.31	.76
6	Insufficient power supply makes me dislike the use of online learning.	18	116	101	65	2.29	.87
7	There is adequate usage of virtual library by pre-service teachers because they always satisfy with information they got from the library	37	113	150	0	2.62	.69
8	I like online learning because it eases my learning process.	171	61	68	0	3.34	.82

9.	I like online learning because it is more useful for other purposes.	91	130	79	0	3.04	.75	
10	I like Online learning because it improves my ICT skills	37	113	150	0	2.62	.69	
Weighted Average		2.77						

Key; SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

Decision Value: 0.00-2.44=Negative, 2.45 – 4.00=Positive

Table 1 shows the pre-service teachers attitude towards the use of online learning in public universities in Ondo State. It was revealed that pre-service teachers dislike online learning because it is time consuming ($x=2.15$), insufficient power supply ($x=2.29$) and it is not accessible ($x=2.31$). However, the result reveals that the pre-service teachers have a positive attitude towards online learning because it makes information easier ($x=3.00$), information through online are accurate ($x=3.03$), did not use online learning because it is expensive ($x=3.15$), it makes learning easier ($x=3.34$) and I like Online learning because it improves my ICT skills ($x=2.62$). Based on the value of the weighted average (2.77 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls within the decision value for positive, it can be inferred that the pre-service teachers' attitude towards the use of online learning in public universities in Ondo State is positive.

Table 2: Level of Utilization of Online learning by Pre-Service Teachers

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.D
1	I often access relevant information for any academic works through online learning	108	48	22	122	2.47	1.33
2	I use online learning because it improves my knowledge on social media.	75	94	29	102	2.47	1.19
3	I always source materials for class, assignment through the use of online learning.	87	94	6	113	2.51	1.26
4.	I have access to online learning facilities	57	121	41	81	2.51	1.08
5.	I use online tools learning facilities	65	117	47	71	2.58	1.07
6	I use online learning for exchange of resources and discussion on my academic work.	96	69	20	115	2.48	1.28
7	I do not have access to use online learning effectively	58	113	60	69	2.53	1.04
8	My smartphone makes it possible for me to use online learning	93	85	17	105	2.55	1.25

9.	The incorporation of school WIFI has motivated massive usage of online learning	51	147	23	79	2.56	1.05
10	Using online learning assist me in creating a socially collected community of learners.	55	135	32	78	2.55	1.06
Weighted Average						2.52	

Key; SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

Decision Value: 0.00-1.49=Low, 1.50 – 2.44=Average, 2.45-4.00 = High

Table 2, shows the utilization of online learning by the pre-service teachers in public universities in Ondo State. The table shows that the pre-service teachers agreed to all the items on the table as follows: I often access relevant information for any academic works through online learning (x=2.47), use online learning because it improve my knowledge on social media (x=2.47), always source materials for class, assignment through the use of online learning (x=2.51), have access to online learning, facilities (x=2.51), use online learning for research purpose (x=2.58), use online learning for exchange of resources and discussion on my academic work (x=2.48), do not have access to use online learning effectively (x=2.53), their smartphone makes it possible for to use online learning (x=2.55), incorporation of school WIFI has motivated massive. Usage of online learning (x=2.56) and using online learning assist them in creating a socially collected community of learners (x=2.55). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.52 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls within the decision value for high, it can be inferred that the level of utilization of online learning by the pre-service teachers in public universities in Ondo State is high.

H01 : There is no significant gender difference in the attitude of pre-service teachers toward utilization of online learning in public universities in Ondo State, Nigeria..

Table 3: Summary of t-test Showing difference in male and female pre-service teachers. Use of Online Learning in Public Universities in Ondo State.

Test Variable (Utilization)	Grouping Variable (Gender)	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t	Sig.	Remark
UTILIZATION	Male	161	52.14	5.59	298	-.998	.319	Not Significant
	Female	139	52.78	5.38				

Table 3, shows the difference in the use of online learning by male and female pre-service teachers in public universities in Ondo State. The table shows that the mean score for male pre-service teachers is 52.14 while that of female is 52.78. The values of the mean scores do not reveal an appreciable difference. Therefore, there is no significant difference between male and female pre-service teachers use of online learning in public universities in Ondo State. (df = 298; t = -.998; p > 0.05). Hence, hypothesis 1 is retained. This result implies that the level of use of online learning by male and female pre-service teachers are same.

Discussion of Findings

The results revealed that pre-service teachers have positive attitude towards the use of online learning for learning. The finding is consistent with the claims of Akobi and Abidoeye (2019) who find out teachers positive attitude towards the use of ICT. The study further reveals pre-service teachers have high level of utilization of online learning. This could be as a result of pre-service teachers' good knowledge and better ICT skills. This finding is in line with Adeyanju, Abidoeye and Fakuade (2025) who found out high level of ICT utilization for learning by secondary school teachers. On the issue of gender, the study shows no significant difference between male and female pre-service teachers use of online learning in public universities in Ondo State. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Aderele & Abidoeye (2022) who find no significant gender difference in students academic performance in Basic Science and Technology when taught with edutainment instructional package.

Conclusion

This study examined pre-service teachers' attitude and utilization of online learning in public universities in Ondo State. The findings revealed that pre-service teachers have positive attitude towards online learning. The study also revealed that there is no significant difference between male and female pre-service teachers use of online learning in public universities in Ondo State. It was suggested in the study that; online training should be organized for pre-service teachers to equip them with necessary skills and competencies to use online learning tools effectively. The paper also recommended that university management and all tiers of government should make provision for online infrastructures available in all universities so as to enable both male and female pre-service teachers have access to online learning facilities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Public university managements should organize training and workshops for pre-service teachers to acquire necessary skills to use online training tools the more.
2. Appropriate facilities and equipment for effective use of online learning should be provided in public universities to encourage both male and female pre-service teachers have access to online learning facilities and develop more positive attitude towards the use of online learning in Ondo State.

References

- Abidoye James A. & Fakuade Victor O. (2025) Students' Perception and Use of Emerging Technology in Tertiary Institutions in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Rima International Journal of Education* 4(1) 1-8 <https://rijessu.com/currentissue/>
- Abidoye, J. A. and Aderele, S. O. (2019). Undergraduates Opinion of Relevance and Challenges of e-Learning in the Teaching of Social Studies in Tertiary Institutions in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Science and Technology Education*, 2(2); 143-151
- Aderele S.O. and Abidoye J.A. (2022) Effect of Edutainment Package on Primary School Pupils' Academic Performance in Basic Science and Technology in Irele Local Government Area of Ondo State. *ABSU Journal of Educational Studies* 9(1) 219-225.
- Albrahim, F. A. (2020). Online Teaching Skills and Competencies. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology* 19(1), 9 - 20.
- Akobi, C. and Abidoye, J. A. (2019). The Roles of Information and Communication Technology

(ICT) Education in Economic Development in Nigeria. *Studies in Education*, 19(1), 140-147.

Ali, W. Online and Remote learning in Higher Education Institutes: A Necessity in light of COVID-19 Pandemic. *High Educ. Stud.* 2020, 10, 16-25.

Baytiyeh, H. (2018). Online learning during post-earthquake school closures". *Disaster International Journal*, 27(2), 215-227. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPM-07-2017-0173>

Folorunso O. Ogunseye O. S. & Sharma S. K. (2006). An Exploratory study of the critical factors affecting the acceptability of e-learning in Nigerian Universities. *Information Management and Computer Security* 14(5): 496-505.

Muirhead, R. (2007). E-learning: Is this teaching at students or teaching with students? *Nursing Forum*. 42(4), 178-184.

Ogundare S.A., Animasahun V.O. and Abidoye J.A. (2022) Lecturers' knowledge and self-efficacy to employ Digital Technologies for Curriculum Instruction in Tertiary Institutions in North-East, Nigeria. *Ilorin Journal of Education*. 42 (1) 72-79

Singh, V. and Thurman, A. (2019). How many ways can we define online learning? A systematic literature review of definitions of online learning (1988-2018). *American Journal of Distance Education*, 33(4), 289-306.

Tariq, H. S. and Rachna, G. (2018). E-Learning for Higher Education. A Case Study. *Journal of Advance Research in Dynamical & Control Systems*. 10(4), 1539 – 1545